

World Data System – International Technology Office

Harvestable Metadata Services: Use Cases from the World Data System

20 Jan 2023

Alicia Urquidi Díaz
Research Assistant for the WDS International Technology Office
ito-ra1@oceannetworks.ca

Karen Payne
Associate Director for International Technology, World Data System
ito-director@oceannetworks.ca

Aude Chambodut
Centre de Données astronomiques de Strasbourg; International Service of Geomagnetic Indices
aude.chambodut@unistra.fr

Robert S. Chen
Columbia Climate School Center for International Earth Science Information Network
bchen@ciesin.columbia.edu

Liu Chuang
Global Change Data Publishing and Repository
lchuang@igsnr.ac.cn

Robert R. Downs
Columbia Climate School Center for International Earth Science Information Network
rdowns@ciesin.columbia.edu

Simon Flower
WDC-Geomagnetism (Edinburgh); INTERMAGNET
smf@bgs.ac.uk

Bu Kun

WDC-Renewable Resources and Environment; Northeast Institute of Geography and Agroecology, Chinese Academy of Sciences

bukun@osgeo.cn

Mayra I. Oyola

International GNSS Server

mayra.i.oyola@jpl.nasa.gov

Sri Vinay

Columbia Climate School Center for International Earth Science Information Network

sri@ciesin.columbia.edu

Juanle Wang

WDC-Renewable Resources and Environment; Geographic Sciences and Natural Resources Research, Chinese Academy of Sciences

wangjl@igsnrr.ac.cn

Yinghua Zhang

Global Change Data Publishing and Repository

zhangyinghua@igsnrr.ac.cn

Qi Xu

National Space Science Data Center; National Space Science Center, Chinese Academy of Sciences

xuqi@nssc.ac.cn

A REPORT BY THE

World Data System • International Technology Office

Funded under the Digital Research Alliance of Canada (The Alliance)

Cite this report:

Urquidi Díaz, A., & Payne, K. (2023). Harvestable Metadata Services Development: Use Cases from the World Data System. World Data System - International Technology Office. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5997733>.

This work is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. To view a copy of this license, visit <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/> or send a letter to Creative Commons, PO Box 1866, Mountain View, CA 94042, USA.

World Data System –
International Technology Office

Ocean Networks Canada
University of Victoria
#100-2474 Arbutus Rd. Victoria, BC V8N 1V8
P 250 472 4527 | wds-ito.org

Table of Contents

Executive Summary	1
Global Change Research Data Publishing and Repository	1
User community	2
Infrastructure Overview	2
Current state of metadata	2
Planned development	2
Resources	3
Challenges	3
International Real Time Magnetic Observatory Network and WDC-Geomagnetism (Edinburgh)	3
User community	3
Infrastructure Overview	4
Current state of metadata	4
Planned development	4
Challenges	5
Technical	5
Planning	5
International GNSS Service	6
User community	6
Infrastructure Overview	7
Current state of metadata	7
Planned development	8
Resources	8
Challenges	8
International Service of Geomagnetic Indices	8
User community	9
Infrastructure Overview	9
Current state of metadata	9
Planned development	9
Resources	10
Challenges	10
National Space Science Data Center	10
User community	11
Infrastructure Overview	12
Current state of metadata	12

Planned development	13
Metadata and standards development	13
Technical and system development	13
Resources	13
Challenges	14
Socioeconomic Data and Applications Center	14
User community	14
Infrastructure Overview	15
Current state of metadata	15
Planned development	16
Resources	16
Challenges	16
World Data Center for Renewable Resources and Environment	16
User community	17
Infrastructure Overview	17
Current state of metadata	18
Planned development	18
Resources	19
Challenges	19
Acknowledgements	19
Notes	19
References	20

Executive Summary

This report describes seven metadata publishing use cases currently employed in World Data System member repositories. The use cases were collected during meetings of the Harvestable Metadata Services Working Group (sometimes referred to as the HMetS-WG) of the World Data System (WDS) International Technology Office (ITO). The working group met in two, 6-month phases over 2020 and 2022. The first phase took place between June and November of 2020 and the second phase, between July 2021 and January 14, 2022. The participants in the working group represent repositories that serve a range of scientific communities, including geomagnetism, environmental and earth observation, global satellite navigation, space science, and socioeconomic studies. Moreover, these repositories represent a global community of practice that serve researchers around the world, with representatives based in China, the UK, France, and the USA. In all cases save one, each repository is described by 6 facets: their user community, their infrastructure, the current state of their metadata and its planned development, their resources and their challenges. The only exception is the lack of information about the resources available to the International Real-time Magnetic Observatory Network and WDC-Geomagnetism (Edinburgh).

Global Change Research Data Publishing and Repository

The Global Change Research Data Publishing and Repository (GCdataPR),¹ a WDS regular member, is a scientific publisher and research data repository. It is one of eight Chinese members of the WDS, as well as one of 20 national data centers sponsored by the Chinese Academy of Sciences (CAS).² Other sponsors include the Institute of Geographic Sciences and Natural Resources Research,³ and the Geographical Society of China.⁴

GCdataPR also serves as the data publisher and repository for partner journals (GCdataPR 2021) in the China-GEOSS⁵ network (Zhang et al. 2019), which is a part of the Group on Earth Observations (GEO) Global Earth Observation System of Systems (GEOSS).⁶ Internationally, it provides the data publishing and sharing infrastructure for CODATA's Task Group on Preservation of and Open Access to Science and Technology Data in/for/with Developing Countries (PASTD, CODATA 2018).

The repository's collection includes articles and data emerging from research activities in "the sustainable environment, especially in geography, environment, natural resources, ecology and the humanities, at the various scales, including global, regional, national, and local spatial scales, as well as different time periods, such as geological, historical, to near

real-time" (Editorial Office of JGCDD 2017: 253). Data articles, datasets, data products and their associated metadata are linked through identifiers and retrieved in search queries as associated content (J. Wang, Bu, et al. 2020). GCdataPR has received wide recognition, including national and international awards for its integrative approach to data sharing and, like NSSDC (see section [the NSSDC section below](#)), GCdataPR is an American Geophysical Union (AGU) recommended community repository (Ma, Duan, and C. Liu 2019).

User community

The intended users of GCdataPR data are researchers in global change research, in China and worldwide. In this respect, it's important to note that all contents (articles as well as the metadata records for both, articles and datasets) are available two languages, Chinese and English.

Infrastructure Overview

GCdataPR publishes peer-reviewed, open-access research data papers through its Journal of Global Change Data & Discovery. The associated datasets are published in the Digital Journal of Global Change Data Repository. In addition to datasets linked to the Journals data papers, GCdataPRs data publishing service is used by 15 Chinese and international partner journals (GCdataPR 2021) in the China-GEOSS network.

GCdataPR maintains real-time usage statistics on its website, including citations, visits, unique visitors, and downloads. Additionally, GCdataPR provides article-level and dataset-level statistics on the object landing pages, and statistics about authors who publish to the repository (Editorial Office of JGCDD 2017). Citation metrics are provided to GCdataPR through Clarivate's Data Citation Index (DCI).⁷ To date, the repository holds more than 800 curated datasets that have undergone quality control checks.

Current state of metadata

All metadata records for datasets and articles are created in English and Chinese. To date, they are available as CrossRef⁸ records, through China-GEOSS, the China National Knowledge Infrastructure (CNKI)⁹ and through DCI. Unlike the NSSDC, these metadata records are not harvested by the National Basic Science Center. Journal and dataset metadata in DCI format is provided to Clarivate once a year via email, as a single .xml file.

The repository mints DOIs for the datasets and data papers through the Chinese DOI registering agency, a DOI Registration and Service Center operated by the Institute of Scientific and Technical Information of China (ISTIC) (Chinese DOI 2012). Author identifiers used are either ResearcherID (Web of Science Group 2021) from Web of Science or ORCID (ORCID 2019).

Planned development

GCdataPR is seeking to become more visible to the global change research community, and to improve the use rate of the research data in the repository.

Resources

As mentioned above, sponsors for GCdataPR are the Institute of Geographic Sciences and Natural Resources Research, the Chinese Academy of Sciences and the Geographical Society of China.

Challenges

GCdataPRs greatest challenge has been finding the resources to sustain its (free) data publishing services, due to its role within the China-GEOSS network and heavy data-curation workload. As for many other repositories, engaging with researchers and promoting research data management and data sharing practices continues to be a challenge for GCdataPR.

International Real Time Magnetic Observatory Network and WDC-Geomagnetism (Edinburgh)

The International Real-time Magnetic Observatory Network (INTERMAGNET)¹⁰ is a federation of 127 digital magnetic observatories (INTERMAGNET 2021) that share near real-time geomagnetism data across the global network. As declared in its statement, INTERMAGNET's mission is to "[e]stablish and maintain an organization with a worldwide membership drawn from institutes operating geomagnetic observatories that is dedicated to building a network of geomagnetic observatories supplying consistent data, with the geographical coverage, quality, and timeliness of delivery required to meet the evolving needs of research and applied science." (INTERMAGNET et. al. 2020)

As a WDS Network member, INTERMAGNET supports data services by maintaining its geomagnetic observatory data collection and dissemination infrastructure (Love and Chulliat 2013). It does so primarily by mandating geomagnetism data standards related to instruments and measurements, as well as standards for data formats, data processing and data transmission. It also provides technical support and advice to observatory operators implementing those standards.

A Regular member of WDS, the WDC-Geomagnetism (Edinburgh)¹¹ is a repository for geomagnetism data hosted at the British Geological Survey (BGS) (Reay et al. 2013). It co-hosts and participates in INTERMAGNET. Both institutions are connected closely through their joint infrastructure. For this reason, both are treated together in this report.

User community

INTERMAGNET's Principles, Conditions, and Policies (INTERMAGNET et. al. 2020: 2-3) describe the networks target community as consisting of members of the scientific community, such as geomagnetism researchers and their organizations, primarily the International Association of Geomagnetism and Aeronomy (IAGA).¹² The document also describes the terms under which INTERMAGNET provides data products for commercial uses.

Infrastructure Overview

The primary output from a geomagnetic observatory has traditionally been continuous recording of the Earth's magnetic field at 1-minute sample period. Due to the complexity of the recording technique, which requires manual observations of the magnetic field at regular intervals combined with continuous automated recording, construction of a final definitive dataset takes some time to achieve. For these reasons INTERMAGNET collects a number of different products from observatories:

1. Preliminary data is collected as close as possible to real-time (the shortest lag time being a few minutes from collection to distribution)
2. Quasi-definitive data is collected within 3 months of recording and has a well-defined error margin with respect to the final data
3. Definitive data is collected at the end of a calendar year and takes some time to check and assemble into an annual publication.

Since 2012, INTERMAGNET has also been collecting 1-second data from observatories. Preliminary and quasi-definitive data from all these sources is transmitted to INTERMAGNET's Geomagnetic Information Nodes (GINs). Definitive data is transmitted to INTERMAGNET via a dedicated ftp server at the Paris GIN. Observatories have traditionally derived other cadence datasets from the main 1-minute data (hourly, daily, and annual means) to aid understanding of the Earth's processes occurring at different frequencies. INTERMAGNET collects these other data products from observatories as part of the publication of definitive data. It is a policy of INTERMAGNET that observatories are responsible for creating all data INTERMAGNET receives and checks data, but does not create or derive it on behalf of an observatory. All datasets are accessible through a search interface at the network's home page, hosted by Earthquakes Canada, where copies of each dataset may also be downloaded via an FTP server. The Earthquakes Canada archive is due to relocate to BGS in 2022.

Current state of metadata

During the course of the HMetS-WG, INTERMAGNET was going through a comprehensive review of the standards supported by the network, and an updated technical manual was published in the summer of 2020.

The INTERMAGNET website features a metadata catalogue¹³ of definitive datasets documented using the IAGA2002 (IAGA Working Group V-DAT 2015) metadata standard. Recently, the group has been depositing the yearly definitive datasets (referenced above) into the data repository of the German Center for Geo-Research (GFZ Potsdam),¹⁴ itself an operator of INTERMAGNET observatories. With the GFZs data publishing services, INTERMAGNET creates DOIs and landing pages with metadata that is compliant with the GFZs GeoJSON, DataCite and ISO 19115 specifications. The definitive datasets deposited at GFZ Potsdam thus far cover 1991 to 2018 and they can be found on the GFZs FTP server, along with their metadata.

Planned development

Aware of the enormous potential of near real-time geomagnetic data, INTERMAGNET is looking for ways to make preliminary data more widely accessible and interoperable. As a rule, the closer a product is to definitive, the longer it must take to be shared, as each type involves processing steps (e.g., adjusting, baseline corrections or filling gaps) and

quality controls. Thus, INTERMAGNET's long-term goal is to open up avenues in which preliminary datasets can be shared more widely, and to develop integration and interoperability within a real-time point network of data. This would open possibilities for collaboration with other researcher communities, both within the space and earth science domains, and in interdisciplinary collaboration initiatives across research fields.

During the analogue era geomagnetic observatories traditionally published paper-based year-books of data, which, along with the data itself, contained a wealth of information about how the data was recorded. This allowed researchers in future years (after the observatory staff were no longer available to consult) a clear description of the activities at an observatory that might have given rise to what appears to be anomalous results. In the digital era, less of this information has been published, and the information that is published is provided at a lower level of detail. Such information that has been published is not structured and is difficult to analyze across the network of recording stations. A metadata development project is underway to address this issue, not only for INTERMAGNET observatories (which comprise about 2/3 of the observatories worldwide), but for all observatories recording geomagnetic data worldwide that are combined by INTERMAGNET with metadata records held at the WDC for Geomagnetism, Edinburgh.

Challenges

Technical

1. Time-series data tools, technologies and standards development appear to lag behind those for geospatial data, which are more advanced and well developed than the bulk of the INTERMAGNET data inventory. Sharing metadata for provisional data types through conventional harvesters and aggregators presents technical challenges, because aggregation (e.g., via OAI-PMH) is typically reliant on persistent identifiers assigned to unique, unchanging datasets.
2. Future-proofing new developments: INTERMAGNET is currently investigating the advantages and disadvantages of adopting general, extensible data and metadata standards in order to make the data pliable enough for future, currently unknown avenues of research and collaboration, versus well defined and more rigid use-case based approaches that tailor data and metadata to better support standards implemented by known communities of practice.
3. It is a significant undertaking to engage the entire community to gather even the simpler parts of the metadata described in the previous section. The metadata system as it exists presently must be accepted into the community and tested at scale before it can be further developed to accommodate the detail required to achieve the goals described above.

Planning

Support and resources for development projects are contingent upon host institutions budget and priorities. Much of the work is done on a volunteer basis by researchers based in INTERMAGNET's partner organizations. With limited resources, it is crucial to invest in the technologies that will support the network's long-term goals.

International GNSS Service

The International Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSS) Service (IGS)¹⁵ is a Network Member of WDS. It can be described as a voluntary federation of over 200 institutions from more than 100 countries, working together to generate high-precision GNSS data and data products (Johnston, Riddell, and Hausler 2017). Outside WDS, the network is also closely embedded in other data sharing federations worldwide, including GEOSS and the Committee on Earth Observation Satellites (CEOS).¹⁶ IGS is also member of various United Nations committees (Villiger and Dach 2019a: 14).

GNSS is one of four international space geodesy services and observing techniques along with Satellite Laser Ranging (SLR) systems, Very Long Baseline Interferometry (VLBI) Doppler Orbitography and Radio positioning Integrated by Satellite (DORIS) ground beacons. It is hard to overstate the importance of IGSs contribution to the GNSS in creating the fundamental tools in all mapping, orientation and navigation services: the Earth Orientation Parameters (EOPs) that make up the International Terrestrial Reference Frame (ITRF), such as Universal Time (UT), length-of-day (LOD), polar motion and polar motion rate. IGS is committed to making these data products widely known and available to the broader public.

The federated structure of IGS and a thorough description of each role can be found on the IGS website (IGS Central Bureau 2021a) and in a dedicated chapter of the Springer Handbook of Global Navigation Satellite Systems (Johnston, Riddell, and Hausler 2017). New developments in the IGS system are proposed and implemented in various member committees and working groups, and coordinated by the IGS Central Bureau, located in Pasadena, California at NASAs Jet Propulsion Lab. The Central Bureau represents IGS in the HMetS-WG.

IGS Data Centers (DCs) include six Global DCs, which are located at NASA's Crustal Dynamics Data Information System (CDDIS),¹⁷ in the United States; the French Institut National de l'information Géographique et Forestière (IGN);¹⁸ the Scripps Institution of Oceanography (SIO)¹⁹ in the United States; the European Space Agency (ESA)²⁰ in Spain; the Korean Astronomy and Space Science Institute (KASI);²¹ and Wuhan University, in China. Regional and Operational DCs, as well as the IGS network of tracking stations (IGS Central Bureau 2021b) distributed across 506 locations worldwide, are listed on the IGS website (IGS Central Bureau 2021a). Though IGS data assets are primarily based on IGS Network tracking sites, IGS has also begun tracking signals from Russia's Global Navigation Satellite System (GLONASS), the European Union's Galileo navigation satellite system, China's BeiDou Navigation Satellite System (BDS) system, Japan's Quasi-Zenith Satellite System (QZSS, also known as Michibiki) and other Space-Based Augmentation Systems (SBAS) (Johnston, Riddell, and Hausler 2017).

User community

As we describe below (under Planned development) both legacy and new IGS data services are being developed to meet the needs of established and new users (Ventura-Traveset, Navarro, and Romero 2019). Principal users of IGS data are found within IGS itself: staff at Analysis Centers, fundamental product coordinators, participants in pilot

projects and working groups (Villiger and Dach 2019a: 139). There is a constant inflow of new members to the organization.

Moreover, all users of modern mapping, orientation and navigation systems are beneficiaries of the work done by IGS individuals, enterprises, non-profits, institutions, and government actors worldwide. To reach non-member users of IGS services, the Central Bureau has established various channels for outreach and communication (*ibid.*: 22). including social media outlets (e.g., tweets about common applications of GNSS data, using the #GNSS4impact hashtag). Part of the aim is to make the general public aware of this foundational yet invisible infrastructure that is ever present in our daily life. Such visibility helps IGS advocate for the organization and make a strong case to its supporting partners, especially in matters of funding.

Infrastructure Overview

IGS data assets are prodigiously large, and consist of multiple types of data, datasets, and derived data products. The complete list of IGSs assets is described in a dedicated section on the network's website (IGS Central Bureau 2020) as well as the CDDIS website (CDDIS 2021).

The IGS data federation infrastructure is a hierarchical, distributed system with many redundancies, with the Receiver INdependent EXchange (RINEX) as the main standard for data exchange within the network (*ibid.*). The system's design ensures that data assets are secure and continuously available, and that network traffic is well distributed. Four specialized types of data centers (DCs) are assigned different roles in data management and data product creation, and each of them delivers outputs to higher-tier DCs. Global DCs are the central interface for most IGS data users, and Regional DCs host content from their assigned region of coverage. Analysis Centers (ACs) are responsible for creating derived data products. ACs create, combine and send these products back to data centers, who store and distribute them among users using the SSR v1.0 standard for GNSS data representation (IGS Central Bureau 2019).

Today, the complete collection of IGS data is distributed across data centers. Only two complete mirrors exist, maintained in separate repositories at CDDIS and the European Space Agency. In 2018, the European Space Agency (ESA) GNSS Science Support Centre (GSSC) located in Madrid started an initiative to create additional mirrors, in a project that also contemplates a new service platform: the IGS Global Data Centre.

Current state of metadata

At present, collection-level metadata records for IGS products can be discovered through the metadata search/retrieval endpoints at NASA's Common Metadata Repository (CMR) (Noll and Michael 2019: 156). Each collection is assigned a DOI, which links to CDDIS's main GNSS sub-site. The individual data products can be searched for on the CDDIS platform, and file downloads are available to registered users. Like other NASA EOSDIS data products, the metadata records for IGS collections in CDDIS are available using a variety of established metadata formats, specifically: DIF 10, ECHO 10, ISO 19115-2:2009 (MENDS and SMAP dialects), and UMM-C. ISO 19115-1:2013 may be supported in the future (Reiter and Rincione 2019).

Planned development

Since 2019, the CDDIS has been working together with the European Space Agency (ESA) GNSS Science Support Centre to create additional data mirrors as well as a new, state-of-the-art IGS data discovery and exploitation platform with an extensive suite of API-based services for data discovery, collaboration and analysis targeted at multiple user groups (Noll and Michael 2019: 156). The ESA IGS Global Data Centre already hosts a mirror server, and the Data Centers have been working through 2020 and 2021 to develop advanced data discovery and workspace services, including tools for data analysis based on JupyterLab (Ventura-Traveset, Navarro, and Romero 2019: 166).

Resources

The voluntary, federated character of this organization also relies on decentralized funding schemes for projects and initiatives, usually by public institutions, governments, or other research organizations. To maintain its reliable service provision, IGS must rely on system redundancy and on multi-year support commitments from the institutions that host the key elements in the system (IGS Central Bureau 2021a). In its most recent strategic plans, IGS has made explicit the need to work towards more stable funding sources for IGS (Villiger and Dach 2019b). A large part of this work is making IGS work visible to the general public in ways that can be measured and reported back to funders, such as through citation of IGS data, products, and other published outputs (IGS Central Bureau 2018).

Challenges

In addition to the funding challenges just described, harmonizing approaches and standards is and will remain an ongoing challenge in a massively large federation such as IGS.

International Service of Geomagnetic Indices

The International Service of Geomagnetic Indices (ISGI)²² is a Regular member of the WDS. It is hosted in Strasbourg, France by the School and Observatory of Earth Sciences (EOST) at the University of Strasbourg, and the French National Centre for Scientific Research (CNRS). ISGI is an international service of the International Association of Geomagnetism and Aeronomy (IAGA), itself one of the 8 associations that make up the International Union of Geodesy and Geophysics (IUGG). While ISGI and INTERMAGNET are in the same field, there is no explicit mention of collaboration between these use cases in any of the documentation we reviewed. We are aware that some coordination work amongst ISGI, INTERMAGNET, the World Data Centre for Geomagnetism and IMAGE (International Monitor for Auroral Geomagnetic Effects) is currently underway at the European Plate Observing System (EPOS).

Though centralized at EOST, ISGI services are provided by a federation of six collaborating institutes, known as ISGI-CIs. It is ISGI's task to centralize the services supplied by each of the CIs, coordinating their collaboration, and ensure the curation and homogeneity of the data products. ISGI's main scientific products, geomagnetic indices, are used to describe (or quantify) the activity level of external magnetic fields (IAGA 2022). Indices are derived from raw magnetic observatory data, using an original algorithm that is

developed by SGI-CIs. Responsibility for each index is assigned to individual institutes (ISGI [2013b](#)).

User community

ISGI's established user base can be found in research organizations in academia, the private and public sectors (e.g. military, telecommunications), and subject areas from geosciences and geophysics, predominantly solid earth physics and space climate/weather. More broadly, geomagnetism data can be a source of insight for any research initiative that is interested in the relationship between the sun and earth's magnetic field. In recent years, new users in the biological sciences are emerging. Other studies in behavioral biology examine geomagnetism's role in organisms as varied as insects (Wajnberg et al. [2010](#)), dogs (Hart et al. [2013](#)), humans (J. Wang, Sun, et al. [2013](#)), and ruminants (Begall et al. [2008](#); Burda et al. [2009](#)). One recent study examines the role of magnetoreception in birds' spatial cognition, orientation and migration (R. Wiltschko and W. Wiltschko [2019](#)).

Infrastructure Overview

ISGI has been tasked with deriving and disseminating IAGA publications and data products. The products, which are endorsed by IAGA and exposed on the ISGI repository, include geomagnetic as well as data series datasets, IAGA bulletins, and lists of remarkable magnetic events. ISGI's completely bespoke repository platform is hosted in the University of Strasbourg's website. Data assets are time series data in IAGAs ASCII Exchange Format, IAGA2002 (WG V-DAT and IAGA [2016](#); IAGA Working Group V-DAT [2015](#)). IAGA-endorsed (ISGI [2013b](#)) indices are highlighted. In addition, ISGI also hosts data for indices that haven't yet been in use long enough to be eligible for IAGA endorsement (ISGI [2013a](#)). Despite this, compared to other geoscience repositories, e.g. GNSS or seismology, ISGI's datasets are small in size.

Current state of metadata

The data lifecycle and workflows are coordinated in close collaboration with ISGI-CIs. Data content at ISGI is well documented, but records are not yet organized into collections with homogeneous metadata. When ISGI's metadata catalogue is complete, crosswalks into DataCite and DCAT are planned.

Planned development

Through an implementation plan for harvestable metadata services, ISGI is seeking to enhance its products visibility and citations. Many ISGI and ISGI-CI products are used widely, but they are sparsely or improperly cited (e.g. identifiers are not included in citations).

Creating FAIR metadata, which can be aggregated by mainstream harvesting services, is a key step towards furthering ISGI's repository maturity. ISGI's plan for harvestable metadata services includes the following components:

1. ISGI has a plan underway to adopt IVOA tables on JSON and CDF and adopt a PID system. Time series datasets will obtain DOIs, which will be minted by each of the ISGI-CIs.
2. A metadata template and schema, with mandatory and optional elements, to be checked or filled by each ISGI-CI, will be developed and built into ISGI's

workflows.

3. The harvesting platform(s) targeted must be supranational, but their ideal subject coverage would be midway between general and specialized. For that reason, ISGI is creating an OAI-PMH service to share ISGI data as DCAT and DataCite, to be harvested by OpenAIRE (at a minimum into the regional European infrastructure).

Resources

ISGI is a volunteer-run organization, with occasional support from its host institutions. To the summer of 2020, ISGI had a 0.5 FTE to support the implementation of a harvestable metadata service.

Challenges

1. ISGIs activities are constrained by its governance structure as a federation: Apart from the work involved in coordinating and sharing products from a distributed service, ISGIs decisions about standards involve extensive exchange and agreement with all of its members.
2. In selecting these standards, a balance must be struck between metadata that is as complete as possible, to fulfill the needs of historical stakeholders, while also capable of adequately describing new outputs (e.g. a different version of the same metadata) for new stakeholders. Specialists should be able to find all the information they require, and the wider public should get the information deemed essential for an efficient use of data.
3. ISGI data products are provided as a service by the IAGA community, but there are concerns that data users don't understand how to use them, or assume them to be in the public domain and don't cite them improperly.
4. Metadata should support the right kind of citation, with credit given to the ISGI-CI as data creator/data provider.

National Space Science Data Center

The Chinese National Space Science Data Center (NSSDC)²³ is a national level repository for space science data, which recognized by the Ministry of Science and Technology and the Ministry of Finance in China. It is also an institutional repository for the National Space Science Center (NSSC, formerly the Center for Space Science and Applied Research) of China Academy of Sciences (CAS) in Beijing (NSSDC 2020c). Furthermore, it is a discipline repository of CAS in the field of space science. It is a WDS Regular Member, and a CoreTrustSeal certified data repository (Edmunds 2020). Together with WDC-RRE and GCdataPR, NSSDC is one of the original nine Chinese data repositories who joined the ICSU system of World Data Centers in 1988.

As per the decree of Measures for Managing Scientific Data , issued in March 2018, by the General Office of the State Council, NSSDC assumes the responsibility of ensuring long-term stewardship and reliable service of space science data in China, specifically as follows:

1. Undertake the task of integrating and archiving space science data.
2. Be responsible for classifying, processing, analyzing and mining of space science data.
3. Safeguard scientific data and promote open sharing of space science data according to laws and regulations.
4. Strengthen the exchange and cooperation in space science data at home and abroad.

Like its Chinese counterparts in the working group, NSSDCs mission and goals are aligned with Chinas current open science policies (Zhang et al. 2019), the joint 2019 CAS and CODATA Beijing Declaration on Research Data (CODATA 2019) and global open science initiatives such as those driven by the Research Data Alliance (RDA), the International Science Council (ISC), the Committee on Data for Science and Technology (CODATA) and the WDS. The repository expresses their commitment to the principles of open data: open as the normal routine and non-open as the rare exception.

The NSSDC is affiliated to the National Space Science Center (NSSC), CAS, and the NSSC spearheads Chinese space science research in the fields of space physics, space environment, microwave remote sensing, and space engineering technology. NSSC is also the key institute responsible for planning, developing, launching and operating Chinas space science satellite missions (NSSC 2015). As NSSC's repository, NSSDC undertakes the task of project repository for CAS Strategic Priority Programs on Space Science, and is engaged in the management, processing, generation and archiving of the space science data for a series of satellite missions, such as Dark Matter Particle Explore, Hard X-ray Modulation Telescope, etc. Furthermore, NSSC has contributed to the space science e-Science progress, for example by building the STAR-Network, a space science cloud e-Science platform within China's Domain Cloud for Space Science and Technology Projects (DCSST) (Zou, Xiong, and Hu 2020). The STAR-network portal has integrated a number of data application and analysis tools and has obtained acceptable application results and serving effects in satellite missions.

User community

The designated community for the NSSDC consists of a wide range of users of space physics, lunar and planetary sciences, space astronomy, and space engineering applications. Users are typically from universities and research institutions, e.g., Peking University, the Institute of Geology and geophysics of CAS, and the National Satellite Meteorological Center. NSSDC established an expert committee to provide guidance and consultation for top-level planning. There are 9 academicians of CAS and Chinese Academy of Engineering, and 7 winners of National Science Funds for Distinguished Young Scholars in the NSSDC Expert Committee (NSSDC 2021b). Most experts on the expert committee are chief scientists or chief designers for major national space science projects, such as Meridian Project, Chinas space science satellite missions, Lunar Exploration Project, Mars Exploration Project, BeiDou navigation GNSS system, etc. They also work in main scientific research institutions and units in the field of space science.

Outside of a small set of protected data assets (discussed below under Challenges), most of the repository's data is openly shared with registered users of the platform under Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike 4.0 International (CC BY- NC-SA 4.0) license (Creative Commons 2016). There are English and Chinese versions of the repository, both of which utilize a single authentication mechanism that allows NSSDC to

understand data usage patterns beyond raw metrics and shed light onto users requirements and experiences of the platform.

Infrastructure Overview

Like the other WDS repositories in China, NSSDC is a high-profile member of national and international data sharing networks. NSSDC's data sources are primarily national space science programs and projects, including:

1. CAS Strategic Priority Programs on Space Science: Hard X-ray Modulation Telescope (HXMT), Dark Matter Particle Explorer (DAMPE), Gravitational wave high-energy Electromagnetic Counterpart All-sky Monitor (GECAM), etc.
2. Chinese Meridian Project
3. Geospace Double Star Exploration Program
4. Lunar Exploration Program ChangE-1 mission, ChangE-2 mission, ChangE-3 mission, and ChangE-4 mission.

Data assets are concentrated in 4 fields of space physics, space astronomy, lunar and planetary sciences, space engineering and application. The data content covers the space range from as close as the sun, to interplanetary space, to near-Earth space, as far as the solar system and even farther cosmic space. Available data products can be traced back to 100 years ago and the physical elements of data products involve hundreds of species. At present, NSSDC has built 23 specialized databases in those 4 fields and has completed the storage and update of 887 datasets. The total amount of data resources held by NSSDC is about 1.7PB.

Data types in NSSDC include images, numerical data, and video. Repository data files use widely accepted common formats in the field, such as FITS (FITS Working Group and Commission 5: Documentation and Astronomical, International Astronomical Union 2016), VOTable (IVOA 2019), CDF (M. Liu 2020), and some specific formats such as those utilized in the SAO Explorer (UMLCAR 2021). All datasets at the NSSDC are organized in accordance with the NSSDC Scientific Data Organization Model (NSSDC 2020b). In terms of multi-disciplinary data resource descriptions, datasets of space physics and planetary science are described based on the SPASE Data Model (Roberts et al. 2018) and PDS4 Information Data Model (PDS4 Information Model Specification Team and NASA 2020) respectively. Services currently offered on the NSSDC platform include a data search portal, the Virtual Space Science Observatory (VSSO, NSSDC 2021a), a data deposit and publishing service for datasets associated with journal publications (SADR, NSSDC 2020d), and iSPACE (NSSDC 2020a), and a toolkit for data mining and analysis.

Current state of metadata

Repository metadata and datasets are served via the NSSDC website, with a Chinese and an English search interface. Within the broader CAS digital research infrastructure, both data catalog and metadata are shared via the Science and Technology Resources Sharing Network and Scientific Data Center of CAS (NSTI 2021). A single collection in the repository, the data from the GeoSpace Double Star Exploration Program, is available via the European Space Agency (ESA) website.

At present, two sets of standards are used in parallel to structure the centers metadata: the NSSDC Core Metadata and disciplinary metadata. The NSSDC Core Metadata Specification is used for internal unified management of data resources. The elements of

NSSDC Core Metadata Specification cover the registration requirements of the Scientific Data Center of CAS ([ibid.](#)) and the China Science and Technology Resource Sharing Network (CNIC and CAS [2020](#)), as well as 3 types of PIDs: DOI, Handle, and CSTR (China Science & Technology Resource identifier, Yuan Yaqin [2021](#)). Based on the NSSDC Core Metadata, NSSDC can perform the unified registration and publication of datasets and can maintain the released data catalogs. This also supports the synchronous releasing of data catalogs to the CAS Data Cloud portal and the China Science and Technology Resources Sharing Network. In terms of disciplinary metadata, NSSDC adopts SPASE (v2.0.0, Roberts et al. [2018](#)) as the metadata standard for the datasets of space physics, and the PDS Information Model (PDS4 Information Model Specification Team and NASA [2020](#)) for the datasets of planetary sciences.

Planned development

NSSDC is planning the following upgrades to support its new harvestable metadata services.

Metadata and standards development

1. NSSDC datasets will add 2 new standards: the DataCite Metadata Schema (DataCite Metadata Working Group [2019](#)) and the VO (IVOA [2019](#)) data model.
2. The SPASE standard currently used by NSSDC datasets will be updated to the new version, and to interoperate with the Virtual Observatory data model.
3. Expanding the NSSDC Core Metadata Standard to include provenance metadata and measures for quality assurance.

Technical and system development

1. Creating an OAI-PMH endpoint within the existing NSSDCs bespoke system in order to target larger international harvesters such as OpenAIRE.
2. Metadata registration service and database upgrades will be carried out to support the generation of new metadata formats (e.g., DataCite Metadata Schema and VO data model) based on the NSSDC Core Metadata.

Resources

Similar to the other Chinese members of the WDS, the NSSDC has stable funding to support the development of metadata harvesting services from the Chinese Academy of Sciences and the Ministry of Science and Technology of the People's Republic of China. The Technology Department, overseen by the NSSDC Director, is responsible for strategic planning and NSSDC infrastructure improvement. It is also responsible for developing the data system, and the data standard system framework and application tools, among other tasks. A sibling department, Data Resources, is responsible for data integration, management, sharing services and security.

In addition to this, it is worth noting that the Computer Network Information Center of the Chinese Academy of Sciences is one of the long-term technical partners of NSSDC, and it can provide technical support for NSSDC's software development.

Challenges

NSSDC has identified two challenges. The first is balancing their commitment to open data with necessary data protection. NSSDC data sources are collected from a large number of major national projects. NSSDC does not store confidential data, but it does apply a data protection policy to a small subset of its data assets to protect the legitimate rights and interests of project undertakers. Data assets covered under this policy are assigned a protection period. During the protection period data are only open to project-related users. According to the policy, once the protection period expires the data shall be fully open to the public.

The second challenge is overcoming the manpower shortage. To support the new metadata standards and data model, and to clarify the conversion pathway between different types of metadata standards, NSSDC needs to invest in more manpower. In addition, most of the NSSDC datasets and metadata information are in Chinese, it can be expected that a lot of human effort will be required in the process of standardizing the datasets in English. For this reason, the above work has been incorporated into NSSDC daily business work plan for the last 2 years, and the need to supplement human resources has been added to NSSDC's development plan.

Socioeconomic Data and Applications Center

The Socioeconomic Data and Applications Center (SEDAC)²⁴ is a WDS Regular member, and a Distributed Active Archive Center (DAAC) of NASA's Earth Observing System Data and Information System (EOSDIS). The repository lives at the Center for International Earth Science Network (CIESIN) at Columbia University, a department that specializes in on-line data and information management for interdisciplinary research into human interactions with the environment. CIESIN has a particular expertise in managing geospatial data. Like CIESIN, SEDACs subject scope is interdisciplinary. They envision their role as promoting collaborative research through an information gateway connecting data products across the natural, earth and social sciences.

User community

SEDACs target user community is interested in studying human interactions with the environment. SEDACs User Working Group (UWG) represents the user community and provides advice, along with NASA, on strategic matters and on data development and dissemination. The SEDAC UWG meets regularly to ensure that SEDAC's product and service development responds to the perspectives of its diverse community of stakeholders. The UWG members represent a variety of disciplines and serve on a rotating schedule to continually reflect the interdisciplinary perspectives of the user community and provide guidance on current issues that are relevant to the data products and services offered by SEDAC.

Despite having a broad user base, SEDAC seeks to reach larger audiences and further diversify the pool of users of its data products and services by engaging with potential stakeholders through various channels. For example, the website has a section that features third-party projects that reuse SEDAC data. While conducting digital outreach to

promote its products and services through social media platforms, SEDAC also shares original content via a YouTube channel and the photo sharing site Flickr.

With respect to data producers, SEDAC is seeking ways to engage researchers early in the RDM process. One recurring issue is receiving data submissions from authors who are caught off-guard by unexpected, new publisher guidelines. In such cases, earlier communications with SEDAC can help to ensure that researcher's data management plans are sound and that the release of their final data product follows the highest possible quality, curation and publication practices, including adherence to the FAIR Principles, the TRUST Principles for Digital Repositories, the GEO Data Management Principles, and the GEO Data Sharing Principles.

Infrastructure Overview

In 47 thematic collections, SEDACs digital library provides open access to over 260 data assets, all curated by SEDAC and NASA in rigorous curation workflows. SEDAC hosts a range of item types, predominantly raster data, map datasets, map services and tabular data. These datasets, and more than 2000 open access maps, may also be visualized and analyzed directly on SEDACs data discovery platform. As indicated above, SEDAC continually responds to new data development, dissemination, and strategy recommendations provided by the UWG and NASA, based on user perspectives.

The repository's front and back end are hosted on the CIESIN site, at Columbia University. The front end is custom; its last redesign was completed in 2015, and there are current plans for its redesign in the near to mid-term future. SEDACs back end uses Vital Digital Asset Management System, a repository software platform built on Fedora. Originally developed at Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University, Vital product development and support service were recently acquired by Clarivate. Vital and the Fedora Object Repository support OAI-PMH, MARCXML and MIX (Metadata for Images in XML Schema) endpoints for metadata exchange, in addition to common web protocols (TCP/IP, HTTP/HTTPS, SRU, SOAP, and FTP). SEDAC hosts its current Vital instance and conducts all of the repository's administrative tasks.

Current state of metadata

As one of NASAs DAACs, SEDAC disseminates data and metadata using standards conforming to OGC, ISO and NASA's Earth Science Data and Information System (ESDIS) project. SEDAC also actively participates in the development of the ESDIS project. SEDAC metadata is created in FGDC CSDGM and DataCite schemas. During ingest into NASAs Earth Observing System (EOS) Common Metadata Repository (CMR), metadata is converted into the Universal Metadata Model (UMM) and disseminated by NASA in standards adhering to the ISO 191** family. SEDACs data and metadata are syndicated through EOSDIS via the larger CMR, which is the back end of Earth- data Search, the Global Change Master Directory (GCMD) and the International Data Network (IDN). Through IDN, SEDAC data descriptions are funneled into the Global Earth Observations System of Systems (GEOSS). SEDAC metadata is available through IDNs OGC CSW endpoint. Further, the CMR can be directly harvested using a variety of protocols.

DOIs for SEDAC contents are issued by DataCite. dataset landing pages on the SEDAC repository website link to metadata file downloads in XML, HTML and TXT formats. Dublin Core is also used internally, for archival purposes. SEDAC metadata is available via both DataCite and the EOSDIS CMR, which have extensive international and interdisciplinary reach.

Planned development

Alongside continued improvements to optimize SEDACs established syndication pathways, the repository is constantly seeking new channels and formats to disseminate metadata. The aim is to improve the discovery of its products and services across the board, seeking users as well as producers of data, and collaborators in research and in data integration projects among the general public, academic settings, government agencies and the private sector. SEDAC is a CoreTrustSeal certified, mature repository whose experiences are continually shared with the RDM community.

SEDAC plans to begin implementation of new discovery capabilities upon completion of the migration from the current content management system (CMS). The implementation of new discovery capabilities is being planned as part of a migration to the Drupal platform. The first phase of the migration would migrate the current site content. The second phase will include content modifications and functional improvements, such as new discovery capabilities. SEDAC is currently conducting the initial stages of the first phase. Some elements in the current workflow may become obsolete as a result of the migration.

After participating actively in the HMetS-WG, SEDAC has also decided to work with the WDS-ITO on implementing Schema.org markup to their metadata. The ITO has advised SEDAC on a Schema.org implementation and provided the repository with a crosswalk of terms found in FGDC metadata to Schema.org.

Resources

SEDAC is sponsored by EOSDIS. Further, it has been collaborating with the Columbia University Library for over 20 years, as well as with Columbia University's Earth Institute, Columbia Climate School, and the Data Science institute. The latter two are more recent (less than a decade old), but SEDAC is interested in deepening that collaboration.

Challenges

While SEDACs development of harvestable metadata services has been very thorough, its use case highlights the limits of a discovery/findability strategy based on harvestable metadata services alone. As mentioned in the above section, a Schema.org implementation is already underway.

World Data Center for Renewable Resources and Environment

The World Data Center for Renewable Resources and Environment (WDC-RRE, <http://wdcrre.data.ac.cn/>) has been a WDS Regular Member since 2011. Before that, it was one of the first members of ICSUs WDC family, the predecessor of the World Data System, and a CoreTrustSeal-Certified repository since early 2019 (J. Wang, Bu, et al. 2020). The WDC-RRE is based in Beijing at the Department for Geo-Data Science and Sharing at the Institute of Geographic Sciences and Natural Resources Research (IGSNRR), a leading center for the study of geography, resources and the environment of the Chinese Academy of Sciences (CAS) (Edmunds 2019; WDC-RRE 2020). Other institutional affiliations include the Geographical Society of China and the China Society of Natural Resources.

Over the past few decades, the repository has become a cornerstone of Chinas new digital research ecosystem. This included piloting the first national research data archiving project, in a joint initiative with the Ministry of Science and Technology (J. Wang, Sun, et al. 2013). Today, WDC-RRE is also the English portal of the National Earth System Science Data Center in China.

Notably, in its continued, close collaboration with the original group of Chinese World Data Centers (J. Wang, Bu, et al. 2020), WDC-RRE serves as the technical support unit for the WDS China Data Portal, a metadata aggregator for all WDS member repositories in China (Institute of Geographic Sciences and Natural Resources Research and Chinese Academy of Sciences, 2016). This initiative encouraged and supported WDS members in developing harvestable metadata services, using spatial data standards for interoperability that would set them up to be integrated into larger aggregators.

User community

The WDC-RRE's user-group diverse, spanning the general public, government agencies, policy makers and international organizations, with its priority communities largely found amongst academic researchers and students. The latter includes scientific staff and technicians in the fields of earth system science, natural resources, environmental conservation, ecological systems and sustainable development (WDC- RRE 2021).

In addition to WDC-RRE's service catalogue for high-quality, FAIR and open data, metadata and data products, the repository is committed to creating information materials in the public domain for a general audience, and workshops in data sharing practices and technologies geared towards Global South research communities and young researchers (Edmunds 2019).

WDC-RRE's User and Expert Committees integrate user feedback for its user-oriented service portfolio. These committees coordinate with representatives from the various communities served; in turn, their input informs WDC-RRE service maintenance and development (Edmunds 2019).

Infrastructure Overview

As mentioned above, WDC-RRE is a CoreTrustSeal-certified repository (J. Wang, Y. Wang, et al. 2019). Its infrastructure is developed using a strategy that combines national and international standards, and open-source architecture and open source software (CAS and IGSNRR 2016). The repository's stack is made up of a Linux (Debian) operating

system, an Open Source NGINX (OSS NGINX, Sysoev 2021) server and PostgreSQL, and using Python for the web site (TorCMS) and web services. A detailed description of WDC-RREs full cyberinfrastructure can be found in WDC-RREs Framework and Development Strategy document, and the notes on the repository's application to the CoreTrustSeal (Edmunds 2019).

Current state of metadata

WDC-RREs metadata endpoints are built on open and established standards. The metadata catalogues are provided for harvesting through pycsw (geopython 2021), a Python implementation of the OGCs Catalogue Services for the Web protocol (OGC- CSW 3.0.0, Edmunds 2019), and through the OAI Protocol for Metadata Harvesting (OAI-PMH 2.0, Lagoze et al. 2015). In addition to those services, a Search/Retrieve via URL (SRU 1.1.) API enables federated search queries.

Standards for metadata at WDC-RRE include Dublin Core 1.1 and ISO 19115, as well as WDS-RRE's Data Identification and Metadata standards. The latter combines ISO 19115 with relevant Chinese standards (China National Institute of Standardization 2021) for data, metadata and exchange formats (J. Wang 2016). Chinese and international data and metadata identifiers are implemented as well. Metadata services at WDC-RRE include a PID versioning system to create identifiers for dynamic datasets, as well as initiatives to promote accurate and standardized data citation practices (Edmunds 2019).

Planned development

In the WDC-RRE, the metadata subsystem has already been designed and implemented, using the repository's own standards in the system to organize it into the local database. Conversion tools are used to create a version of the metadata for public release, which is served using the OGC-recommended tool Pycsw. The system will continue to be modified based on feedback from maintenance staff and end users.

Future updates include developing an independent map application system, based on WebGIS technology. At present, released scientific datasets provide map thumbnails, but many users may hope to learn more about the data in an interactive way, which can be achieved with a web-based GIS interactive map. All geospatial data will be published as a web map server (WMS) using MapServer, while a Leaflet-based development tool on the client side will enable users to easily browse and view the data. The WMS also provides complete metadata information in response to server requests. This update will also improve its current stand-alone Pycsw implementation.

The update will address the platform's applications. Based on current usage and user suggestions, the repository has plans to enhance its web interface to better serve non-expert users. This task will include optimizing the interface layout and the navigation structure and expanding the help sections. The WDC-RRE repository platform is a professional system, whose professional users (data experts and technicians) may understand the platform's back-end well, but non-experts may need more basic instructions and tips to find the information they need.

Resources

For the repository's continuity and future development, the WDC-RRE can count on stable institutional and material support from the IGSNRR, CAS and the NSTIC. Its team of 30 full- and part-time staff is made up of research data management experts, as well as five dedicated IT professionals (Edmunds 2019).

Challenges

A new metadata standard specification has been proposed to solve issues of inter-connectedness and understanding of the repository's information in the larger system. While multiple organizations and research teams have made great efforts to build standards and software implementations, the data center island or silo phenomenon is still an issue: It is still a challenge to establish a data sharing network with data centers functioning as nodes.

Acknowledgements

Support for the Harvestable Metadata Services Group was funded by the Digital Research Alliance of Canada (formerly New Digital Research Infrastructure Organization, NDRIO) under Collaborative agreement number 51387-5032. The contributions of Robert R. Downs were supported by the National Aeronautics and Space Administration under Contract 80GSFC18C0111 for the Socioeconomic Data and Applications Distributed Active Archive Center (DAAC). The paper's publication was supported by the Global Change Data Publishing and Repository (GCdataPR).

This work represents the perspectives of the authors and does not necessarily reflect those of their sponsors or employers.

Notes

1. Global Change Research Data Publishing and Repository, <http://www.geodoi.ac.cn/weben/>
2. Chinese Academy of Sciences, <https://www.cas.cn/>
3. Institute of Geographic Sciences and Natural Resources (IGSNRR), <http://www.igsnr.cas.cn/>
4. Geographical Society of China, <http://www.gsc.org.cn/>
5. China-GEOSS, <https://www.chinageoss.cn>
6. Global Earth Observation System of Systems (GEOSS), <https://earthobservations.org/geoss.php>
7. Data Citation Index, <https://clarivate.com/webofsciencegroup/solutions/webofscience-data-citation-index/>
8. CrossRef, <https://www.crossref.org/>
9. China National Knowledge Infrastructure, <https://www.cnki.net/>
10. International Real-time Magnetic Observatory Network, <https://intermagnet.github.io/>
11. WDC-Geomagnetism (Edinburgh), <http://www.wdc.bgs.ac.uk/>
12. International Association of Geomagnetism and Aeronomy, <http://www.iaga-aiga.org/>
13. IMOs and Definitive Data (beta), <https://intermagnet.github.io/metadata/>

14. German Center for Geo-Research, <https://dataservices.gfz-potsdam.de/portal/>
15. International GNSS Service, <https://igs.org/>
16. Committee on Earth Observation Satellites, <https://ceos.org/>
17. Crustal Dynamics Data Information System, <https://cddis.nasa.gov/>
18. Institut National de l'Information Géographique et Forestière, <https://www.ign.fr/>
19. Scripps Institution of Oceanography, <https://scripps.ucsd.edu/>
20. European Space Agency, <https://www.esa.int/>
21. Korean Astronomy and Space Science Institute, <https://www.kasi.re.kr/kor/index>
22. International Service of Geomagnetic Indices, <http://isgi.unistra.fr/>
23. National Space Science Data Center of China, <https://www.nssdc.ac.cn/eng/>
24. Socioeconomic Data and Applications Center, <https://sedac.ciesin.columbia.edu/>

References

- Begall, Sabine et al. (Sept. 2008). "Magnetic alignment in grazing and resting cattle and deer". In: *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 105.36, pp. 13451–13455. doi: [10.1073/pnas.0803650105](https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0803650105). (Visited on 01/18/2023).
- Burda, Hynek et al. (Apr. 2009). "Extremely low-frequency electromagnetic fields disrupt magnetic alignment of ruminants". In: *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 106.14, pp. 5708–5713. doi: [10.1073/pnas.0803650105](https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0803650105). (Visited on 01/18/2023).
- CAS and IGSNRR (2016). *The Specification of WDS-RRE Data Identification*. url: <http://wdcrr.data.ac.cn/static/upload/ee/ee56cfd4-3fba-11e8-b4ea-1866dae73633.pdf> (visited on 01/18/2023).
- CDDIS (2021). *GNSS data and product archive*. url: https://cddis.nasa.gov/Data_and_Derived_Products/GNSS/GNSS_data_and_product_archive.html (visited on 01/18/2023).
- China National Institute of Standardization (2021). *Chinese Standard GB/T, GBT, GB*. url: <https://www.chinesestandard.net/Index.aspx> (visited on 01/18/2023).
- Chinese DOI (2012). *About Us*. url: <http://www.chinadoi.cn/portal/newsAction!about.action?type=1> (visited on 01/18/2023).
- CNIC and CAS (2020). *China Science and Technology Cloud*. url: <https://www.cstcloud.net/cstcloud/> (visited on 01/18/2023).
- CODATA (2018). *Preservation of and Access to Scientific and Technical Data in/for/with Developing Countries (PASTD)*. url: <https://codata.org/initiatives/task-groups/previous-tgs/preservation-of-and-access-to-scientific-and-technical-data-in-for-with-developing-countries-pastd/> (visited on 01/18/2023).
- CODATA (2019). *The Beijing Declaration on Research Data*. Chinese Academy of Science. Tech. rep. Beijing, China. url: http://english.cnic.cas.cn/rsearch/rp/201912/t20191231_228855.html (visited on 01/18/2023).
- Creative Commons (2016). *Share your work*. url: <https://creativecommons.org/share-your-work/> (visited on 01/18/2023).

- DataCite Metadata Working Group (2019). *DataCite Metadata Schema Documentation for the Publication and Citation of Research Data v4.3*. Technical documentation. doi: [10.14454/7XQ3-ZF69](https://doi.org/10.14454/7XQ3-ZF69). (Visited on 01/18/2023).
- Editorial Office of JGCDD (2017). "Guidelines of Global Change Research Data Publishing & Repository". In: *Journal of Global Change Data & Discovery* 1.3, pp. 253–261. doi: [10/gksr27](https://doi.org/10/gksr27). (Visited on 01/18/2023).
- Edmunds, Rorie (2019). *WDC - Renewable Resources and Environment. Notes Before Completing the Application*. Tech. rep. CoreTrustSeal. url: <https://www.coretrustseal.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/02/WDC-Renewable-Resources-and-Environment.pdf> (visited on 01/18/2023).
- Edmunds, Rorie (2020). *National Space Science Data Center. Notes Before Completing the Application*. Tech. rep. CoreTrustSeal. url: <https://www.coretrustseal.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/10/Chinese-National-Space-Science-Data-Center.pdf> (visited on 01/18/2023).
- FITS Working Group and Commission 5: Documentation and Astronomical, International Astronomical Union (2016). *Definition of the Flexible Image Transport System (FITS)*. url: https://fits.gsfc.nasa.gov/standard40/fits_standard40aa-le.pdf (visited on 01/18/2023).
- GCdataPR (2021). *Global Change Research Data Publishing & Repository*. url: <http://www.geodoi.ac.cn/WebEn/Sponsors.aspx> (visited on 01/18/2023).
- geopython (Mar. 2021). *geopython/pycsw*. url: <https://github.com/geopython/pycsw> (visited on 01/18/2023).
- Hart, Vlastimil et al. (Dec. 2013). "Dogs are sensitive to small variations of the Earth's magnetic field". In: *Frontiers in Zoology* 10.1, p. 80. doi: [10.1186/1742-9994-10-80](https://doi.org/10.1186/1742-9994-10-80). (Visited on 01/18/2023).
- IAGA (2022). *Products & Services*. url: <https://iaga-aiga.org/data-products-services/> (visited on 01/18/2023).
- IAGA Working Group V-DAT (2015). *IAGA-2002 Exchange Format*. url: <https://www.ngdc.noaa.gov/IAGA/vdat/IAGA2002/iaga2002format.html> (visited on 01/18/2023).
- IGS Central Bureau (2018). *IGS Strategic Plan 2017*. Strategic Plan. International GNSS Service. url: <https://kb.igs.org/hc/en-us/articles/360001150012-2017-Strategic-Plan> (visited on 01/18/2023).
- IGS Central Bureau (2019). *IGS Terms of Reference Revision 190724*. url: <https://files.igs.org/pub/resource/IGS-Terms-of-Reference-2019.pdf> (visited on 01/18/2023).
- IGS Central Bureau (2020). *Data and Products*. International GNSS Service. url: <https://www.igs.org/data-products-overview/> (visited on 01/18/2023).
- IGS Central Bureau (2021a). *Data*. en-US. url: <https://www.igs.org/data/> (visited on 01/18/2023).
- IGS Central Bureau (2021b). *Network*. url: <https://www.igs.org/network/> (visited on 01/18/2023).
- INTERMAGNET (2021). *Map of Observatories*. Leaflet digital map. url: <https://intermagnet.github.io/metadata/#/map> (visited on 01/18/2023).
- INTERMAGNET et. al. (2020). *Global magnetic observatory data 1991 - 2015*. doi: [10.5880/INTERMAGNET.1991.2015](https://doi.org/10.5880/INTERMAGNET.1991.2015) (Visited on 01/18/2023).
- ISGI (2013a). *Index Criteria for endorsement of indices by IAGA*. url: https://isgi.unistra.fr/index_criteria.php. (visited on 01/18/2023).
- ISGI (2013b). *IAGA ENDORSED GEOMAGNETIC INDICES/EVENTS*. url: https://isgi.unistra.fr/about_indices.php (visited on 01/18/2023).
- IVOA (2019). *IVOA Recommendation - VOTable Format Definition*. url: <https://www.ivoa.net/documents/VOTable/> (visited on 01/18/2023).
- Johnston, Gary, Anna Riddell, and Grant Hausler (2017). "The International GNSS

- Service". In: *Springer Handbook of Global Navigation Satellite Systems*. Ed. by Peter J.G. Teunissen and Oliver Montenbruck. Springer Handbooks. Cham: Springer International Publishing, pp. 967–982. doi: [10.1007/978-3-319-42928-1_33](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-42928-1_33). (Visited on 01/18/2023).
- Lagoze, Carl et al. (2015). *Open Archives Initiative - Protocol for Metadata Harvesting - Guidelines for Repository Implementers*. Tech. rep. url: <http://www.openarchives.org/OAI/2.0/guidelines-repository.htm#MinimalImplementation> (visited on 01/18/2023).
- Liu, Michael (2020). *CDF Home Page: What is Common Data Format (CDF)?* url: <https://cdf.gsfc.nasa.gov/> (visited on 01/18/2023).
- Love, Jeffrey J. and Arnaud Chulliat (2013). "An International Network of Magnetic Observatories". In: *Eos* 94.42, pp. 373–374. doi: [10.1002/2013EO420001](https://doi.org/10.1002/2013EO420001) (visited on 01/18/2023).
- Ma, J. H., Z. Q. Duan, and C. Liu (2019). "GCdataPR Identified as the Trusted Repository by American Geophysical Union to Deposit the Original Data from Research Paper". In: *Journal of Global Change Data & Discovery* 3.3, pp. 305–307. doi: [10.3974/geodp.2019.03.13](https://doi.org/10.3974/geodp.2019.03.13) (visited on 01/18/2023).
- Noll, Carey and Patrick Michael (2019). "CDDIS Global Data Center Technical Report 2019". In: *International GNSS Service: Technical Report 2019*. Ed. by Arturo Villiger and Rolf Dach. IGS Technical Reports. Bern, Switzerland: IGS Central Bureau, Bern Open Publishing. isbn: 978-3-03917-009-8. doi: [10.7892/boris.144003](https://doi.org/10.7892/boris.144003). (Visited on 01/18/2023).
- NSSC (2015). *A Snapshot of NSSC*. url: <http://english.nssc.cas.cn/au/ac/> (visited on 01/19/2023).
- NSSDC (2020a). *iSPACE*. url: <http://ispace.nssdc.ac.cn/> (visited on 01/19/2023).
- NSSDC (2020b). *NAIS Management Processes*. Tech. rep. v. 1.0. China: National Space Science Data Center. url: <https://www.nssdc.ac.cn/eng/file/NAIS%20Management%20Processes.pdf> (visited on 01/19/2023).
- NSSDC (2020c). *National Space Science Center*. url: <http://english.nssc.cas.cn/> (visited on 01/19/2023).
- NSSDC (2020d). *NSSDC SADR*. url: <https://sadr.nssdc.ac.cn/ours/use> (visited on 01/19/2023).
- NSSDC (2021a). *(National Space Science Data Center)*. url: <https://vsso.nssdc.ac.cn/mhsy/html/vssoindex.html> (visited on 01/19/2023).
- NSSDC (2021b). *Expert Committee*. Portal. url: https://www.nssdc.ac.cn/eng/about_us.html (visited on 01/19/2023).
- NSTI (2021). *China Science and Technology Resources Sharing Network*. url: <https://www.escience.org.cn/> (visited on 01/19/2023).
- ORCID (2019). *About ORCID*. url: <https://info.orcid.org/what-is-orcid/> (visited on 01/19/2023).
- PDS4 Information Model Specification Team and NASA (2020). *PDS4 Information Model Specification*. url: https://pds.nasa.gov/datastandards/documents/im/v1/index_1F00.html (visited on 01/19/2023).
- Reay, Sarah et al. (Feb. 2013). "Operations of the World Data Centre for Geomagnetism, Edinburgh". In: *Data Science Journal* 12. Num Pages: 5 Publisher: Committee on Data for Science and Technology (CODATA) of the International Council for Science (ICSU), WDS47–WDS51. issn: 1683-1470. doi: [10/gkczmj](https://doi.org/10/gkczmj). url: https://www.jstage.jst.go.jp/article/dsj/12/0/12_WDS-005/_article (visited on 01/19/2023).

- Reiter, Erich and Joseph Rincione (2019). *CMR Data Partner User Guide*. url: <https://wiki.earthdata.nasa.gov/display/ED/CMR+Data+Partner+User+Guide#CMRDataPartnerUserGuide-DataPartnerTasks> (visited on 01/19/2023).
- Roberts, D. Aaron et al. (2018). "The SPASE Data Model: A Metadata Standard for Registering, Finding, Accessing, and Using Heliophysics Data Obtained From Observations and Modeling". In: *Space Weather* 16.12, pp. 1899–1911. doi : [10.1029/2018SW002038](https://doi.org/10.1029/2018SW002038) (visited on 01/19/2023).
- Sysoev, Igor (Mar. 2021). *OSS NGINX*. url: <https://github.com/nginx/nginx> (visited on 01/19/2023).
- UMLCAR (2021). *SAO Explorer*. url: <https://ulcar.uml.edu/SAO-X/SAO-X.html> (visited on 08/20/2021).
- Ventura-Traveset, Javier, Vicente Navarro, and Ignacio Romero (2019). "GSSC Global Data Center Technical Report 2019". In: *International GNSS Service: Technical Report 2019*. Ed. by Arturo Villiger and Rolf Dach. IGS Technical Reports. Bern, Switzerland: IGS Central Bureau, Bern Open Publishing. doi: [10.7892/boris.14400](https://doi.org/10.7892/boris.14400). (Visited on 01/19/2023).
- Villiger, Arturo and Rolf Dach (2019a). *International GNSS Service: Technical Report 2018*. Technical report. International GNSS Service. doi: [10.7892/boris.130408](https://doi.org/10.7892/boris.130408). (visited on 01/19/2023).
- Villiger, Arturo and Rolf Dach, eds. (2019b). *International GNSS Service: Technical Report 2019*. IGS Technical Reports. Bern, Switzerland: IGS Central Bureau, Bern Open Publishing. doi: [10.7892/boris.14400](https://doi.org/10.7892/boris.14400). (Visited on 01/19/2023).
- Wajnberg, Eliane et al. (Apr. 2010). "Magnetoreception in eusocial insects: an update". In: *Journal of The Royal Society Interface* 7. suppl_2, S207–S225. doi: [10.1098/rsif.2009.0526.focus](https://doi.org/10.1098/rsif.2009.0526.focus) (visited on 01/19/2023).
- Wang, Juanle (2016). *WDC-RRE Metadata Standard v.1.0*. Standard. Beijing: World Data Center for Renewable Resources and Environment. url: <http://wdcrre.data.ac.cn/static/upload/79/79654602-3fb9-11e8-bf87-1866dae73633.pdf> (visited on 01/19/2023).
- Wang, Juanle, Kun Bu, et al. (Aug. 2020). "Progress in Activities of WDS-China Data Centers". In: *Data Science Journal* 19.1, p. 33. doi: [10.5334/dsj-2020-033](https://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2020-033) (visited on 01/19/2023).
- Wang, Juanle, Jiulin Sun, et al. (Feb. 2013). "A New Approach to Research Data Archiving for WDS Sustainable Data Integration in China". In: *Data Science Journal* 12. doi: [10.2481/dsj.WDS-020](https://doi.org/10.2481/dsj.WDS-020) (visited on 01/19/2023).
- Wang, Juanle, Yi Wang, et al. (Nov. 2019). "Practice in the CoreTrustSeal Certification of World Data Center". In: 1.3, pp. 71–81. doi: [10.19788/j.issn.2096-6369.190307](https://doi.org/10.19788/j.issn.2096-6369.190307) (visited on 01/19/2023).
- WDC-RRE (2020). *Introduction*. url: <http://wdcrre.data.ac.cn/page/introduction> (visited on 01/19/2023).
- WDC-RRE (2021). *WDC-RRE Catalogue Server*. Beijing, China. url: <http://wdcrre.data.ac.cn/csw/> (visited on 01/19/2023).
- Web of Science Group (2021). *ResearcherID*. url: <https://webofscience.help.clarivate.com/en-us/Content/wos-researcher-id.htm#rid-for-researchers> (visited on 01/19/2023).
- WG V-DAT and IAGA (2016). *IAGA2002 Data Exchange Format*. url: <https://www.ngdc.noaa.gov/IAGA/vdat/IAGA2002/iaga2002format.html> (visited on 01/19/2023).
- Wiltschko, Roswitha and Wolfgang Wiltschko (Sept. 2019). "Magnetoreception in birds". In: *Journal of The Royal Society Interface* 16.158. doi: [10.1098/rsif.2019.0295](https://doi.org/10.1098/rsif.2019.0295) (visited on 01/19/2023).

- Yuan Yaqin (Jan. 2021). *The practice of China Science & Technology Resource identifier (CSTR) in National Space Science Data Center (NSSDC)*. doi: [10 . 5281 / zenodo.4474952](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4474952) (visited on 01/19/2023).
- Zhang, Lianchong et al. (Dec. 2019). "Approach and practice: integrating earth observation resources for data sharing in China GEOSS". In: *International Journal of Digital Earth* 12.12, pp. 1441–1456. doi: [10 . 1080 / 17538947 . 2018 . 1504995](https://doi.org/10.1080/17538947.2018.1504995) (visited on 03/02/2021).
- Zou, Ziming, Senlin Xiong, and Xiaoyan Hu (2020). "Chapter 4 - e-Science Applications of Chinas Space Science Satellite Missions". In: *Chinas e-Science Blue Book 2018*. Ed. by CAS et al. Singapore: Springer Singapore, pp. 63–84. url: https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-981-13-9390-7_4 (visited on 01/19/2023).